

Magnetic Field of a Moving Charge Follows from a Piece of the Electric Field in the Rest Frame?

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If one considers a charge Q at rest, it has an electrostatic field such that $q\phi$ is potential energy. If q is along the y axis and the charge Q and q move along the x -axis with constant velocity v , then this is the scenario seen from a frame moving with $-v$. For a Lorentz transformation $y=y'$ and the force in the moving frame should still be along y' . In fact, $d/dy\phi$ should be proportional to this force because $(0, q\phi)$ transforms to $(qAc, q\phi')$ where $A=v\phi$ and $\phi' = \phi / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. One may transform x, y, z variables into x', y', z' variables in the moving frame, but $y'=y$ and $z'=z$. If the force along the y -axis is still proportional to $d/dy\phi$, we wish to consider $E' = -q\text{grad}'\phi' - qdA/dt'$ partial and $q v \times B$ where $B = \text{grad}' \times A$. If v is in the x direction, E' (y component) $= -q / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} d/dy\phi$. If the total force in the y direction is still $d/dy\phi$, then $q v \times B$ should be proportional to $d/dy\phi$.

We try to use the identity from (1): $\text{grad}(F \cdot G) = (F \cdot \text{grad})G + (G \cdot \text{grad})F + F \times \text{grad} \times G + G \times \text{grad} \times F$ where F and G are vectors. We first verify this identity and use $F \text{ vector} = v$ (constant in the x direction) and $G = A = v\phi$ (in the x direction) to show that:
 $v \times B = \text{grad}(v \cdot A) - (v \cdot \text{grad})A$ which is proportional to $d/dy\phi$. We are not aware if this approach has been shown before or not. We also show that the same conclusion follows even without using the vector identity.

Thus, we argue that the magnetic force in the moving frame is really proportional to $d/dy\phi$ from the rest frame. In other words, for a charge, the magnetic field is not a new phenomenon, but really proportional to the electrostatic force in the y direction for motion in the x .

Charge At Rest and As Seen from a Frame Moving with Constant $-v$

A charge Q at rest has a potential ϕ and potential energy is $q\phi$ which transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector under a Lorentz transformation. If q is along the y axis and the velocity is along the x , then $y'=y$ and the force should still be along the y axis in the moving frame.

We first consider the Lorentz transformation on $(0, q\phi)$:

$$\begin{aligned} |qAc| &= |g \ vg| |0| & ((1)) \quad \text{where } g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \\ |q\phi'| &= |-gv \ g| |q\phi| \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Thus: } \phi' = g\phi \text{ and } Ac = vg\phi \quad ((2))$$

Here $\phi'(x, y, z)$, but one may apply a Lorentz transform to these to rewrite them in terms of x', y', z' where $y'=y$ and $z'=z$.

At this point, there is no notion of a magnetic field. The force as seen in the moving frame, however, should be along the y axis. In the rest frame this force is $q-d/dy\phi$. In the moving frame: $\phi'=g\phi$ and d/dy' is d/dy , so the force is proportional to the electrostatic y in the rest

frame. (Note: If one considers the full expression: $E' = -\text{grad}' \phi' - d/dt' A$, $A=v \phi$ and v is in the x direction, dA/dt' partial does not contribute to E' in the $y=y'$ direction.

We next ask: Is there a way to show formally that $q d/dy \phi$ is proportional to $q v \times B$ where $B = \text{grad} \times A$?

Vector Identity and a Link Between $-q \text{grad} \phi$ and $q v \times (\text{grad} \times A)$

In (1) page 174, the following vector identity is presented, where F and G are vectors:

$$\text{Grad} (F \cdot G) = (F \cdot \text{grad}) G + (G \cdot \text{grad}) F + F \times \text{grad} \times G + G \times \text{grad} \times F \quad ((3))$$

As a first step, we wish to verify this identity using $d_j = d/dx_j$ and $d_{il} = \delta_{il}$ as symbols.

$$d_i (f_j g_j) = f_j d_j g_i + g_j d_j f_i + e_{ijk} f_j e_{klm} d_l g_m + e_{ijk} g_j e_{klm} d_l f_m$$

$$= f_j d_j g_i + g_j d_j f_i + [d_{il} d_{jm} - d_{im} d_{jl}] f_j d_l g_m + [d_{il} d_{jm} - d_{im} d_{jk}] g_j d_l f_m$$

$$= f_j d_j g_i + g_j d_j f_i + f_j d_i g_j - f_j d_j g_i + g_j d_i f_j - g_j d_j f_i = d_i (f_j g_j)$$

Thus ((3)) is verified. Next, we wish to set $F = v$ with v being a constant velocity in the x direction and $A = q v \phi$ being G . Then:

$$\text{Grad} (v \cdot A) = (v \cdot \text{grad}) A + v \times (\text{grad} \times A) \quad ((4))$$

If one considers the x direction: $v v d/dx \phi = v v d/dx \phi$.

If one considers the y direction: $v v d/dy \phi = v \times (\text{grad} \times A)$

The electrostatic force along the y direction from the rest frame is really of the same form as the magnetic force $q v \times B$ as seen in the moving frame. Thus, magnetism seems to be the same physical phenomenon as the electrostatic force from a charge at rest.

Result Without Using The Vector Identity

It is possible to obtain the same result without using the above vector identity for this example. In particular, one may ask: Is there an operation involving vectors v and grad acting on $A = q v \phi$ which may yield a result proportional to $-q d/dy \phi$?

If one considers the y component (because physically the force is still in the y direction) of $v \times (\text{grad} \times A)$ for v in the x direction, then one has:

$$e_{ijk} v_j e_{klm} d_l A_m = (d_{il} d_{jm} - d_{im} d_{jl}) v_j d_l A_m = v_j d_i A_j - v_j d_j A_i$$

For v in the x direction and the y component of the above result one has: $v \frac{d}{dy} v\phi$ or $Vv \frac{d}{dy} \phi$. Thus $v \times (\text{grad} \times A)$ is proportional to $\frac{d}{dy} \phi$ which is the electrostatic force form.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to show that the electrostatic force between a charge Q at rest and a charge q , also at rest, some distance away along the y axis is really the essence of the magnetic force seen in a moving frame. To do so, we use as vector identity which links $\text{grad} (F \cdot G)$ to $(F \cdot \text{grad}) G + F \times \text{grad} \times G$, where we choose $G=A$ (magnetic vector potential) and $F=v$ (constant velocity along the x direction) to show that $v \times (\text{grad} \times A)$ is really the same as $\frac{d}{dy} \phi$. We also show that the same result holds even if one does not use the vector identity.

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations fo Electromagnetic Theory (Addison-Wesely, 1980)